

Science Learning Environment and Critical Thinking Skills of Grade 10 Learners in a Last Mile School: Basis for an Intervention Program

Alayu, Trisha Mae M., Pacis, Ma. Suzeth D., Llaneta, Alexis Kurt M., and Cajucom, Elsa L., PhD

Abstract

Teachers' understanding of students' perceptions of their science classroom environment and their critical thinking abilities is key to creating more supportive, engaging, and equitable learning spaces. This study explores how Grade 10 students at Tiblac National High School—an Ambaguio district last mile school—perceive their science learning environment and their own critical thinking skills during SY 2024–2025. Through a descriptive quantitative approach, the research used survey questionnaires to gauge students' views on their classroom environment and a paper-pencil test to measure critical thinking abilities. Findings revealed that students felt their science classes had low personalization, insufficient support, and only moderate inclusivity, with limited opportunities for independent learning and investigative activities. They also reported experiencing moderate participation but concerning instances of exclusion and a lack of recognition for student diversity. Additionally, students perceived that their classrooms allowed some level of autonomy, but the opportunities for investigative learning and differentiated instruction were minimal. Overall, most students' critical thinking skills ranged from poor to average, with only a few showing high proficiency. These results led to tailored recommendations aimed at improving both the classroom environment and critical thinking abilities, especially for last mile schools like Tiblac NHS.

Keywords: abstraction, drawing conclusion, inference, perception, students' independence

Introduction

Teachers' understanding of students' perceptions of their science classroom environment and critical thinking skills is key to creating more supportive, engaging, and equitable learning spaces. Literature highlights the crucial role of critical thinking in 21st-century learning, yet studies show persistent gaps in fostering these skills, especially in marginalized areas such as the Philippines' Last Mile Schools. Previous research, like that of Zhang (2022), Alsaleh (2020), and Kim (2019), has focused on urban settings or general education, leaving a gap in understanding the rural, resource-limited contexts. This study addresses this gap by examining the perceptions of Grade 10 students at Tiblac National High School, a Last Mile School in Ambaguio district, SY 2024–2025. It investigated the science learning environment across personalization, participation, independence, investigation, and differentiation and students' critical thinking levels. The findings aim to guide tailored interventions to improve science education and critical thinking in similar settings.

Statement of the Problem

The study explored how the Grade 10 learners of Tiblac National High School, Ambaguio, perceived the level of perception in their Science Learning Environment and determined their critical thinking skills for SY 2024–2025.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of perception of the Grade 10 learners about their science learning environment in terms of:
 - a. personalization;
 - b. participation;
 - c. independence;
 - d. investigation; and,
 - e. differentiation?

2. What is the level of critical thinking skills of the Grade 10 learners?
3. What intervention program can be designed for the last mile schools?

Methodology

This descriptive quantitative research employed survey questionnaires and a paper-pencil test to assess the science learning environment and critical thinking skills of Grade 10 students at Tiblac National High School. The study included 36 participants from a last mile school, known for limited resources and accessibility challenges.

Results and Discussions

Section 1: Level of Perception of Grade 10 Students about their Science Classroom Environment

Table 1 presents the summary of Grade 10 students' perception about their science classroom environment across all domains.

Table 1

Summary Table on Students' Level of Perception About Their Science Classroom Environment

Domains of Classroom Environment	Area Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of Perception
1. Personalization	2.04	0.34	Low
2. Participation	2.15	0.38	Moderately Participative
3. Independence	2.21	0.33	Moderate Independence
4. Investigation	2.31	0.36	Rarely
5. Differentiation	2.10	0.37	Rarely
Overall	2.16	0.356	

The data on students' level of perception about their science classroom environment, summarized across five domains, reveals an overall moderate but generally low engagement and support atmosphere, as indicated by the overall mean of 2.16 ($S = 0.356$).

Personalization scored the lowest among the 5 indicators for science classroom environment with a mean of 2.04 ($S = 0.34$), indicating a low level of perception in this domain. This suggests students feel the classroom environment does not sufficiently cater to individual needs or personal connections. Participation had a mean of 2.15 ($S = 0.38$), reflecting a moderately participative environment, suggesting limited engagement in classroom activities.

Independence attained a mean of 2.21 ($S = 0.33$), indicating moderate independence. Which implies that Grade 10 students perceive some freedom to work autonomously but it is limited. Lastly, investigation and differentiation both scored low, with means of 2.31 ($S = 0.36$) and 2.10 ($S = 0.37$) respectively, interpreted as rarely occurring. This suggests that inquiry-based learning and tailoring instruction to diverse student needs are infrequent.

The rarity of investigative and differentiated practices highlights a significant gap in applying inquiry-based and student-centered instructional strategies, which are critical for science learning.

Given that classroom environment directly influences student motivation, attitudes, and achievement in science, these findings suggest that improvements in personalization, participation,

independence, investigation, and differentiation could enhance students' learning experiences and outcomes.

Section 2: Level of Critical Thinking Skills of the Grade 10 Students

Table 2 surfaces the distribution of critical thinking skills levels among 36 Grade 10 students, which are categorized into Poor, Average, and High critical thinking skills, with corresponding frequencies, percent, and an overall mean score with standard deviation.

Table 2
Critical Thinking Skills' Level of the Grade 10 Students

Critical Thinking Skills Level	Frequency	Percent	Overall Mean Score (sd)	Description Level
Poor Critical thinking Skills	20	55.60		
Average Critical thinking Skills	15	41.70	16.62	Average Critical
High Critical thinking Skills	1	2.80	(5.45)	Thinking Skill
Total	36	100.00		

Legend: 0 – 15 = Poor Critical Thinking Skills; 16 -30 = Average Critical Thinking Skills; 31 – 45 = High Critical Thinking Skills

The mean score for the group with poor critical thinking skills is 16.62 with a standard deviation of 5.45. The description level for this mean score is noted as "Average Critical Thinking Skill," which suggests that the scoring or categorization might have some overlap or that the mean score is near the threshold between poor and average.

The majority of Grade 10 students, 20 out of 36 (55.6%), fall into the category of "poor critical thinking skills." There are 15 Grade 10 students (41.7%) who are classified as having average critical thinking skills. Meanwhile, only 1 student (2.8%) demonstrates high critical thinking skills.

More than half of the students are identified as having poor critical thinking skills, indicating a need for targeted interventions to improve these skills. Whereas, the very small percent of students with high critical thinking skills suggests that enrichment programs or differentiated instruction could help nurture advanced critical thinking abilities. The level of critical thinking skills among Grade 10 students of Tiblac National High School shared a parallel result with the National Achievement Test for 2018, particularly in the area of critical thinking skills (DepEd, 2022).

Section 3. Proposed Intervention Program for Grade 10 Students of Tiblac National High School

Table 3 presents a detailed summary of the specific findings, corresponding interventions, activities, and strategic approaches aimed at enhancing both the science classroom environment and the critical thinking skills of Grade 10 students at Tiblac National High School.

Table 3
Proposed Intervention Program Based on the Results of the Study

Specific Findings	Interventions	Activities	Strategies
Classroom environment does not sufficiently cater to individual needs or personal connections	Implement student-centered learning approaches such as Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL)	Argument-Driven Inquiry (ADI) to promote scientific argumentation and creative thinking	Differentiation of tasks to meet individual learning needs
Limited engagement and autonomy in the science classroom	Use Research-Based Learning Activities that promote autonomy and engagement	Research projects in units like "Life in the Environment"	Encourage student choice and self-directed investigation
Investigation and differentiation rarely occur	Incorporate Design Thinking combined with STEAM Project-Based Learning (PjBL)	Hands-on experiments and design challenges in chemistry and environmental topics	Scaffold inquiry and problem-solving tasks to enhance critical thinking
More than half of the students have poor critical thinking skills	Develop and use teaching materials based on Science, Environment, Technology, and Society (SETS) framework	Synchronous and asynchronous learning with critical thinking tests and reflective activities	Use formative assessments and feedback to guide critical thinking development

The proposed interventions based on the results of the perceived classroom learning environment and critical thinking skills test among Grade 10 students were aligned with evidence-based practices that will eventually improve academic performance, critical thinking, and student engagement, suggesting a promising pathway to elevate science education quality.

This data-driven intervention leverages well-supported student-centered practices in teaching and learning to possibly address identified weaknesses in the current science classroom, aiming for improved learning outcomes and skill development critical for students' academic and professional futures.

In response to the identified challenges and areas for improvement, the RISE-UP Intervention Program was conceptualized and developed.

The RISE-UP program, with an acronym for **R**eflective, **I**nclusive, **S**tudent-centered, **E**ngaging, and **U**nderstanding-based **P**edagogy, is designed to create a transformative impact on science education through the enhancement of key pedagogical and learning environment elements. Specifically, it targets improvements in student engagement, teacher scaffolding, inquiry-oriented instruction, and the systematic cultivation of critical thinking competencies. These core aspects are aligned with the principles of student-centered learning and inclusive educational practices, thereby ensuring that science instruction remains relevant, equitable, and responsive to the needs of all learners, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

Central to the implementation and success of the RISE-UP program is the pivotal role of science teachers. They are not merely transmitters of content but serve as facilitators of meaningful learning experiences. In this capacity, science teachers are responsible for designing, adapting, and executing instructional strategies that are both inquiry-driven and contextually appropriate. Their responsibilities include planning and leading hands-on, student-centered activities that encourage exploration, hypothesis formation, experimentation, and reflective thinking.

Moreover, science teachers are expected to foster a classroom culture that supports open communication and collaborative problem-solving essential for the enhancement of critical thinking. Through formative assessment techniques, individualized support, and differentiated instruction, teachers guide students toward deeper conceptual understanding and higher-order reasoning. They also act as role models in demonstrating scientific inquiry, ethical reasoning, and lifelong learning.

In a resource-limited educational environment such as Tiblac National High School, the adaptability, creativity, and professional commitment of science teachers become even more vital. Their ability to implement the RISE-UP interventions with limited materials, while still maintaining instructional quality and learner motivation, underscores their integral role in ensuring the long-term sustainability and effectiveness of the program.

Hence, the RISE-UP Intervention Program is a comprehensive, context-sensitive approach designed to address critical gaps in the science learning environment. Its success hinges on the active participation and leadership of science teachers, whose expertise and pedagogical practices are key to fostering a dynamic, inclusive, and intellectually stimulating classroom culture.

Conclusions

The study reveals that Grade 10 students at Tiblac National High School perceived their science classrooms are missing key elements that make learning more engaging and supportive. They reported low levels of personalization and inclusivity, not enough support from teachers, and limited chances to explore through hands-on investigation. While some students perceived themselves as somewhat independent and involved in class, there are still concerns about feeling excluded, a lack of appreciation for diversity, and insufficient efforts to customize instruction to different learning needs.

Alongside these challenges in the learning environment, the students' critical thinking skills are generally rated as poor to average. Only a small number of students show strong critical thinking abilities.

When these factors are considered together, these findings point to a clear and urgent need for change. The study proposes the RISE-UP intervention program to improve the atmosphere in science classrooms and to help students strengthen their critical thinking skills, which is an especially important goal for last-mile schools like Tiblac NHS.

Recommendations

Based on the aforementioned conclusions, the following recommendations were derived:

1. On Science Classroom Environment
 - a. Schools and teachers should consider targeted interventions to improve personalization, such as professional development on inclusive practices, regular feedback mechanisms, and strategies to foster a more welcoming and respectful classroom climate.
 - b. Interventions to include structured participation strategies, explicit norms for inclusivity, and ongoing feedback mechanisms to address the specific issues identified—such as ensuring all voices are heard and valued and preventing students from feeling marginalized—could significantly enhance the participative climate.
 - c. Strengthened the differentiated instructional strategies and flexible learning environments to support diverse learners and improve educational outcomes by providing coaching and mentoring to science teachers, participation to training on differentiation of instruction, and benchmarking of best practices on differentiation.
2. Secondary schools, most especially those in the last mile school areas, should engage their students in meaningful educational activities in the classroom that foster critical thinking

abilities, which are essential for academic success and real-world problem-solving.

3. Forward a copy of the designed intervention program to the Schools Division Office of Nueva Vizcaya through the Curriculum Implementation Division to possibly address challenges in the science classroom environment and critical thinking skills of Grade 10 students in the last mile schools.

References

- Admiraal, W., Post, L., Kester, L., Louws, M., & Lockhorst, D. (2022). Learning labs in a secondary school in the Netherlands: Effects of teachers' autonomy support on student learning motivation and achievement. *Educational Studies*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2021.2023473>
- Alsaleh, N. J. (2020). Teaching critical thinking skills: Literature review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(11), 584-596. https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/11529/critical-thinking-skills-in-education-a-systematic-literature-review.pdf
- Alsaleh, N. J. (2020). Teaching critical thinking skills: Literature review. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 19(1), 21-30. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1239945.pdf>
- Auman, S. (2024). Exploring the impact of physical classroom environment on student engagement in high school English classes. *Nexus International Journal of Science and Education*, 1(1). https://nijse.org/index.php/home/article/view/64?fbclid=IwY2xjawK-mEVleHRuA2FbQIxMQABHguyDelqIG1jRNwlrRom6_hVkBdNewSOHQZkcsVH8yS-cqKlirZE4LyTWMKG_aem_l24V1LMuYF0rFj6XCUqgqg
- Baflor, G. M., & Paglinawan, J. L. (2024). Classroom environment on students' science engagement in private schools. *International Journal of All Research Writings*, 6(5), 328–335. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386349481_CLASSROOM_ENVIRONMENT_ON_STUDENTS%27_SCIENCE_ENGAGEMENT_IN_PRIVATE_SCHOOLS
- Bai, N. (2023). Educational challenges in the Philippines. *Philippine Institute for Development Studies*. <https://pids.gov.ph/details/news/in-the-news/educational-challenges-in-the-philippines>
- Bautista, J. (2023). *PH students are still among the lowest scorers in reading, math, and science – Pisa*. *INQUIRER.net*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1871182/ph-students-still-among-lowest-scorers-in-reading-math-science-pisa#:~:text=For%20the%202022%20assessment%2C%20the>
- Bautista, R. G. (2021). The effects of personalized instruction on the academic achievement of students in physics. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351409677_THE_EFFECTS_OF_PERSONALIZED_INSTRUCTION_ON_THE_ACADEMIC_ACHIEVEMENT_OF_STUDENTS_IN_PHYSICS
- Besar, P. H. S. N. B. P. H. (2018). *Situated learning theory: The key to effective classroom teaching?* <https://doi.org/10.2121/.v1i1.1022>
- Braggs, D. (2018). *The influence of differentiation: Student engagement, academic achievement, and teacher responsiveness to student variances*. Bethel University. <https://spark.bethel.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1898&context=etd>

- Bowie, C. (2018, October 4). *Differentiated instruction leads to increased student engagement*. NISOD. https://www.nisod.org/2018/10/04/xl_32/
- Cabrales, P., & Pacala, F. A. (2023). Science education in the Philippine countryside: A phenomenological study. *Researchgate*. <https://doi.org/10.33222/ijetl.v3i1.2677>
- Chinn, C. A., Yoon, S. A., Hussain-Abidi, H., Hunkar, K., Noushad, N. F., Cottone, A. M., & Richman, T. (2023). Designing learning environments to promote competent lay engagement with science. *European Journal of Education*, 58(3), 407–421. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12573>
- Choi, J., & Hannafin, M. (1995). Situated cognition and learning environments: Roles, structures, and implications for design. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 43(2), 53–69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02300472>
- Cypher Learning. (2022, May 17). *10 ways to provide differentiation in PD for teachers*. K-20 Blog. <https://www.cypherlearning.com/blog/k-20/differentiation-in-professional-development-teacher>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- DepEd RO2, (2019). 2018 National Achievement Test (NAT) 6, 10, and 12 results and analysis. <https://region2.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/2018-NATIONAL-ACHIEVEMENT-TEST-NAT-610-12-RESULTS-AND-ANALYSIS-.pdf>
- Department of Education, (2016). *Republic of the Philippines Department of Education K to 12 curriculum guide science (Grade 3 to Grade 10)*. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Science-CG_with-tagged-sci-equipment_revised.pdf
- Department of Education (2019). *DepEd's Last Mile Schools Program to address gaps in isolated, disadvantaged areas*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/07/22/depeds-last-mile-schools-program-to-address-gaps-in-isolated-disadvantaged-areas/>
- Differentiated Instruction: Strategies and examples for the classroom*. (2023, May 26). Strobel Education. <https://strobeleducation.com/blog/differentiated-instruction-strategies-and-examples-for-the-classroom/>
- Dole, S., Bloom, L., & Kowalske, K. (2015). Transforming pedagogy: Changing perspectives from teacher-centered to learner-centered. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-based Learning*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.7771/1541-5015.1538>
- Eakins, M., Reyes, J., & Santos, L. (2024). Classroom management strategies and school environment on student engagement. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(5), 123–135. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/articles/classroom-management-strategies-and-school-environment-on-student-engagement/>
- Evalle, J. E. (2017). *Library utilization and extent of learning engagement by the third-year students in a State College in Iloilo Province* [Unpublished master's thesis, Central Philippine University, Jaro, Iloilo City]. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12852/1042>
- Facts in Figures, (2024). *Philippines performance in the 2018 and 2022 PISA* https://cpbrd.congress.gov.ph/images/PDF%20Attachments/Facts%20in%20Figures/FF2024-11_Philippines_Perf_in_the_2018_and_2021_PISA.pdf

- Facione, P. A. (2015). *Critical thinking: What it is and why it counts (2015 update)*. Insight Assessment. <https://www.insightassessment.com>
- Fraser, B. (1981). *TTmLE* validity and use of individualized classroom TITLE environment questionnaire: PUB DARE Apr 81*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED204351.pdf>
- Ghafar, Z. N. (2023). The impact of critical thinking on learners to increase their self-regulate in the education process: An Overview. *International Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 1(1), 23–30. <https://doi.org/10.61424/ijah.v1i1.13>
- Gheysens, E., Griful-Freixenet, J., & Struyven, K. (2023). *Differentiated instruction as an approach to establish effective teaching in inclusive classrooms*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-31678-4_30
- Graetz, K. A. (2019). *Chapter 6. The psychology of learning environments*. Educause. <https://www.educause.edu/research-and-publications/books/learning-spaces/chapter-6-psychology-learning-environments>
- Haworth, C. M., Davis, O. S., Hanscombe, K. B., Kovas, Y., Dale, P. S., & Plomin, R. (2013). Understanding the science-learning environment: A genetically sensitive approach. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 23, 145–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2012.07.018>
- Hidayati, A. (2019). *The analysis of influencing factors of learning styles, teacher's perceptions and the availability of learning resources in elementary schools in Padang, West Sumatra*. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1185/1/012149/meta>
- High, N. (2024). *Tiblac National High School · G3CG+2CR, Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines*. <https://maps.app.goo.gl/AYwVYfghcn54Bbn3A>
- Ibragimov, G. I., Murkshtis, M., Zaitseva, N. A., Kosheleva, Y. P., Sadykova, A. R., & Shindryaeva, N. N. (2023). Research trends on learning environment in science education. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education*, 19(11), em2351. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/13680>
- Muhammad Jamil, Yaar Muhammad, & Naima Qureshi. (2021). Critical thinking skills development: Secondary school science teachers' perceptions and practices. *Sjesr*, 4(2), 21–30. [https://doi.org/10.36902/sjesr-vol4-iss2-2021\(21-30\)](https://doi.org/10.36902/sjesr-vol4-iss2-2021(21-30))
- Karampelas, K. (2023). Critical thinking in national primary science curricula. *Eurasian Journal of Science and Environmental Education*, 3(2), 51–60. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ejsee/13271>
- Kim, B. (2019). *Introduction to critical thinking*. https://open.library.okstate.edu/criticalthinking/chapter/_unknown_-2/
- Kennedy, O. O. (2010). *Teaching learning resources and academic performance of students in mathematics in selected secondary schools in Bondo District*. <https://ir.kiu.ac.ug/items/88aa436c-c8da-4092-9c81-4c5c335022ad>
- Lagura, R. T. (2024). Exploring science education in last-mile schools: Experiences and challenges. *International Journal of Religion*, 5(10), 2890–2906. <https://doi.org/10.61707/qh4a9s12>
- Lopez, M. J. D. (2021). Inquiry-based teaching and learning in science: Its extent of implementation, challenges encountered, and learning outcomes among the secondary schools in the division of Aklan, Philippines. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 5(2), 1048–1055.

- <https://www.ijtsrd.com/humanities-and-the-arts/education/38605/inquiry-based-teaching-and-learning-in-science-it%E2%80%99s-extent-of-implementation-challenges-encountered-and-learning-outcomes-among-the-secondary-schools-in-the-division-of-aklan-philippines/mikko-jan-d-lopez>
- Lualhati, G. P. (2018). What is happening in your class? Exploring Filipino science classroom atmosphere. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 2(7), 207–218. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366247871_What_is_Happening_in_your_Class_Exploring_Filipino_Science_Classroom_Atmosphere
- Marcelo, E. (2023). DepEd to prioritize last mile schools. *Philstar.com*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/11/25/2314032/deped-prioritize-last-mile-schools>
- Martin-Dunlop, C. S. (2006). Science learning environments and action research. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234612567_Science_Learning_Environments_and_Action_Research
- McLeod, S. (2024). *Operant conditioning: What it is, how it works, and examples*. Simply Psychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/operant-conditioning.html>
- M C Ghee, D., Lowell, N., & Lemire, S. (2007). *The classroom learning environment (CLE) questionnaire: Preliminary development*. <https://depts.washington.edu/assessmt/pdfs/reports/OEARReport0607.pdf>
- Meirbekov, A., Maslova, I., Shestak, V., & Gallyamova, Z. (2022). Digital education tools for critical thinking development. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 44, 101023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2022.101023>
- Miao, J., & Ma, L. (2022). Students' interaction, self-regulation, and learning engagement in higher education: The importance of social presence to learning. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13(815220). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.815220>
- Otieno, K. O. (2010). Teaching/learning resources and academic performance in mathematics in secondary schools in Bondo District of Kenya. *Asian Social Science*, 6(12). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v6n12p126>
- Pablico, J., Moustapha Diack, & Lawson, A. (2017). Differentiated instruction in the high school science classroom: Qualitative and quantitative analyses. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*. https://www.academia.edu/34196680/Differentiated_Instruction_in_the_High_School_Science_Classroom_Qualitative_and_Quantitative_Analyses
- Pacala, F. A. A. (2022). Discipline-based vs. spiral learning approach to science education: A critical analysis in the Philippine setting. *IJJET (International Journal of Indonesian Education and Teaching)*, 7(1), 41–47. <https://doi.org/10.24071/ijiet.v7i1.5598>
- Pajarillo-Aquino, I. (2019). Academic performance of the College of Teacher Education. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 8(3), Article G-2628. <https://garph.co.uk/IJARMSS/Mar2019/G-2628.pdf>
- Panyukova, S. V. (2020). Student's digital portfolio for assessing and presenting talents. *ITM Web of Conferences*, 35, 02006. <https://doi.org/10.1051/itmconf/20203502006>

- Partnership for 21st Century Learning. (2019). *Framework for 21st century learning*. Battelle for Kids. http://static.battelleforkids.org/documents/p21/P21_Framework_Brief.pdf
- Perez, D. (2022). *Chapter 7: Behaviorism*. Pressbooks. <https://kstatelibraries.pressbooks.pub/dellaperezproject/chapter/chapter-6-behaviorism/>
- Philippine Statistics Authority (2023). *Preliminary 2023 First semester official poverty statistics*. Psa.gov.ph. <https://psa.gov.ph/statistics/poverty/node/1684061846>
- Presnillo, J., & Aliazas, J. V. (2024). Inquiry-based learning for enhanced students' engagement and critical thinking skills in Biology. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Technology*, 10(3), 794–800. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379695792_Inquiry-Based_Learning_For_an_Enhanced_Students%27_Engagement_And_Critical_Thinking_Skills_In_Biology
- Qizi, S. R. S. (2024). The Role of pedagogy in fostering critical thinking skills in students. *International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 4(01), 74–77. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijasr-04-01-12>
- Rajeh Alsalhi, N., Abdelrahman, R., F. I. Abdelkader, A., Salim Al-Yatim, S., Habboush, M., & Al Qawasmi, A. (2021). Impact of using the differentiated instruction (DI) Strategy on student achievement in an intermediate stage science course. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 16(11), 25. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i11.22303>
- Ramos, R. M. T., & Israel, G. F. G. (2024). Students' inquiry and science-related attitude as mediated by self-concept. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 11(11), 847–859. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/5693>
- Reeve, J., & Jang, H. (2006). What teachers say and do to support students' autonomy during a learning activity. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 98(1), 209–218. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.98.1.209>
- Richardson, V. (2003). Constructivist pedagogy. *Teachers College*, 105(9), 1623–1640. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1467-9620.2003.00303.x>
- Santos, L. (2017). The role of critical thinking in science education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(20). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED575667.pdf>
- Servallos, N. J. (2023). Student assessment: Philippines still in bottom 10. *Philstar.com*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/12/06/2316752/student-assessment-philippines-still-bottom-10>
- Second Congressional Commission on Education. (2024). *EDCOM II year one report miseducation. The failed system of Philippine education* <https://edcom2.gov.ph/media/2024/02/EDCOM-II-Year-One-Report-PDF-022924.pdf>
- Sharma, L. R., Bhattarai, R., Humagain, A., Subedi, S. P., Thapa, S., & Acharya, H. (2023). Exploring the underlying ways of enhancing critical thinking skills. *International Research Journal of MMC*, 4(4), 83–96. <https://doi.org/10.3126/irjmmc.v4i4.61939>
- Uzma Shahzadi, Nimmi, & Dr. Itbar Khan. (2020). Exploring the relationship between critical thinking skills and academic achievement. *Sjesr*, 3(1), 236–242. [https://doi.org/10.36902/sjesr-vol3-iss1-2020\(236-242\)](https://doi.org/10.36902/sjesr-vol3-iss1-2020(236-242))
- Supreme Court E-Library, (2018) Republic act no. 11075 - an act establishing a national high school in barangay Tiblac, municipality of Ambaguio, province of Nueva Vizcaya to be known as Tiblac*

- National High School, and appropriating funds therefor.*
<https://elibrary.judiciary.gov.ph/thebookshelf/showdocs/7/95866>
- Ten Dam, G., & Volman, M. (2004). Critical thinking as a citizenship competence: Teaching strategies. *Learning and Instruction, 14*(4), 359-379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2004.06.002>
- Toledo, F. L. (2023). Differentiated instruction for an enhanced students' academic performance in Science 10 (Physics). *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research, 4*(8), 2830–2846. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.08.21>
- United Nations. (2023). *Goal 4: Quality education. The global goals.*
<https://www.globalgoals.org/goals/4-quality-education/>
- Van De Pol, J., Volman, M., & Beishuizen, J. (2010). Scaffolding in teacher–student interaction: A decade of research. *Educational Psychology Review, 22*(3), 271–296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-010-9127-6>
- Webster, R. S. (2019). Using differentiated instruction to support all learners: A case study in inclusive education. *Journal of Education and Learning, 8*(3), 15–23. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1230740.pdf>
- Windschitl, M. (2009). *Cultivating 21st century skills in science learners: How systems of teacher preparation and professional development will have to evolve.*
https://sites.nationalacademies.org/cs/groups/dbasseite/documents/webpage/dbasse_072614.pdf
- William and Mary School of Education, (2020). *The test of critical thinking (TCT) examiner's manual.*https://education.wm.edu/centers/cfge/_documents/resources/tctfinalmanual.pdf
- Zhang, Y. (2022). The research on critical thinking teaching strategies in college English classroom. *Creative Education, 13*(4), 1469–1485. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2022.134090>
- Zohar, A., & Dori, Y. J. (2003). Higher-order thinking skills and low-achieving students: Are they mutually exclusive?. *Journal of the Learning Sciences, 12*(2), 145–181. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327809JLS1202_1